

Research article

First record of *Pochazia shantungensis* (Chou & Lu, 1977) (Hemiptera: Ricaniidae) in Bulgaria: alien and potentially invasive species on Via Pontica

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Abstract: The current study documents the first record of *Pochazia shantungensis*, an invasive pest species in the Ricaniidae family, within Bulgaria. Two specimens were observed and a single male specimen was collected in Burgas, marking a significant expansion in the distribution of this species. Known for its adaptability and agricultural impact, *P. shantungensis* represents a potential threat to native flora and crop systems. This paper provides details on the collection site, specimen identification, and the possible role of the Via Pontica migratory route in the introduction of *P. shantungensis* to Bulgaria. A comparable radiation pathway in a different non-native species of the same family, *Orosanga japonica* (Melichar, 1898), is discussed in the paper. Given the recent spread of *P. shantungensis* into the Western Palaearctic region, monitoring and further studies are recommended to assess its impact on local ecosystems.

Keywords: Black Sea Coast, Bulgaria, non-indigenous, planthoppers, Ricaniidae

Introduction

Monitoring the invasions of different hemipteran species is essential for several ecological, agricultural, and economic reasons. Hemiptera are the largest order of insects with incomplete metamorphosis (Brambila & Hodges, 2008; Weirauch & Schuh, 2011), including a variety of species which are significant agricultural pests and vectors of plant diseases (Schaeffer & Panizzi, 2000). Invasions of Hemiptera are particularly common – about 20% of all non-native insects belong to this order (Liebhold et al., 2024). By tracking their invasion patterns, researchers and policymakers can better understand, predict, and mitigate the impacts these species have on ecosystems and agriculture. *Pochazia shantungensis* (Chou & Lu, 1977), a planthopper of the Ricaniidae family, has recently been identified as an invasive species in several regions of Europe (Bragard et al., 2023), including Turkey (Hizal et al.,

2019, 2023), France (Bourgoin et al., 2020), Italy (Stroiński et al., 2022), Russia (Zhuravleva et al., 2023), Hungary (Schlitt et al., 2024) and Netherlands (den Bieman et al., 2024). Originally native to East Asia, *P. shantungensis* has spread through several pathways, primarily through accidental introductions associated with trade and transportation networks (Bragard et al., 2023). The species poses a significant risk to agricultural systems, having been documented to feed on a range of economically important crops (Hizal et al., 2023). In this paper, we present data about the first record of this non-native planthopper in Bulgaria.

Materials and methods

Live specimen were photographed in situ with Nokia G60. The photograph of insect habitus was made using a Canon EOS R50 camera with a Laowa 90mm

Fig. 1. *Pochazia shantungensis* habitus, lateral view.

F2.8 CA-Dreamer 2X Macro lens. Images were captured at different focal planes using a WeMacro motorised rail, which allowed for automated, precise capture of sequential images with partial focus. These images were subsequently processed with Helicon Focus 8.1.0 software to produce fully focused, composite images for detailed documentation. The specimen was identified based on morphological characteristics as described in previous studies (Stroiński & Bourgoïn, 2022; Park & Jung, 2021). The material is stored in the Zoological collection of Sofia University (BFUS).

Results and discussion

During a visit to a flowers stock and market in Burgas in the beginning of November 2024 two large specimens of planthoppers drew our attention.

One of both specimens was photographed and a single male specimen was collected. The locality and material examined are as follows: a specimen of

Pochazia shantungensis was collected on November 2, 2024, in Burgas, Bulgaria.

Taxonomy

Superfamily Fulgoroidea Latreille, 1807
Family Ricaniidae Amyot & Serville, 1843
Genus *Pochazia* Melichar, 1898

Pochazia shantungensis (Chou & Lu, 1977) (Fig. 1)

Bulgaria: 1 ♂ (BFUS-I-IG030254), (Fig. 1), Burgas, N42.5246° E027.4460°, 37 m a.s.l., on a parking place near flowers stock, 31.x.2024, leg. N. Simov; 1 specimen observed at same date and locality (Fig. 2).

The collected specimen was confirmed as *Pochazia shantungensis* based on diagnostic morphological characteristics, consistent with prior descriptions (Park & Jung, 2021). This finding represents the first record of *P. shantungensis* in Bulgaria and potentially

Fig. 2. *Pochazia shantungensis* in situ, on a car in on a parking place near flowers stock and market in Burgas, Bulgaria.

radiation at least true the Black Sea Coast (Fig. 2). It is worthy of note that the only other representative of the family Ricaniidae in Bulgaria, *Orosanga japonica* (Melichar, 1898), is also non-native. The later was initially found near the seashore in the southern most part of the Bulgarian Black Sea coastline (Gjonov, 2013). The majority of the Bulgarian Black Sea coastline, including the area around Sinemorets (Gjonov, 2013), has been observed to exhibit a gradual expansion of its distribution range. This was evidenced by a record in the vicinity of Primorsko in 2024.

Via Pontica is one of the majors European animal migratory routes through Western Black Sea Coast. Except that it allows the movement of numerous species, including invasive insects (Akner et al., 2022) it is an important trade road since Antiquity facilitating the transport of the goods and movement of large masses of peoples (Staccioli, 2003; Bounegru, 2014).

The record in Burgas, a coastal city on the Via Pontica, suggests a plausible pathway for its introduc-

tion. It should not be ignored and that the species was found near a place where exotic plant species were traded. Our opinion is that the main pathways of introduction and dispersal of its newly recorded alien planthopper in Bulgaria are human activities: ornamental trade and movement as 'stowaways' in transport vehicles, followed by unintentional introduction through natural dispersal across political borders.

The role of Via Pontica in facilitating the dispersal of invasive insects has been documented in other cases and warrants further study regarding its impact on the local biota in the region (Hizal et al., 2019).

The presence of *P. shantungensis* raises concerns due to its potential agricultural impacts, as it feeds on a variety of economically important crops (Akner et al., 2022). Furthermore, the coastal environment around Burgas and nearby ecosystems may be susceptible to infestation, which could lead to ecological and economic impacts if the species establishes and spreads. This finding underscores the importance of

Fig. 3. Map of the collecting point of *Pochazia shantungensis*.

continuous monitoring for early detection and management of invasive species, especially efforts to track its distribution.

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